

Rebuttal to the Yan Report

Author: Adam Cornish, PhD

Abstract

On September 14th, Yan *et al* published some nonsense. There are four big issues with it that scream hoax for me:

1. This is not peer reviewed.
2. This type of study has already been done by respected institutes and published in very respected journals¹⁻⁷, and there are those that have doubled-down on the quality of that research⁸.
3. The ethics surrounding the authors is suspect at best, and intentionally malicious at worse.
4. The science itself is bad.

Conclusion: The Yan Report is bad.

Introduction

On September 14th, Yan *et al* published garbage⁹. It was convincing garbage (kind of like how some things are convincingly not-cake¹⁰), but it was still garbage.

Here, I outline why it was garbage.

Methods

Identify peer review issues.

I went to the Zenodo website and looked for a peer review policy.

Investigate prior research on SARS-CoV-2 evolution.

I went on Google Scholar and searched for papers related to “SARS-CoV-2 evolution”, “SARS-CoV-2 mutations”, and “SARS-CoV-2 genetic identity”.

Identify ethical concerns surrounding the authors.

I googled the authors. I also googled the “Rule of Law Society and Rule of Law Foundation”.

Look for holes in the science.

I read the paper. I also read other papers.

Results & Discussion

Peer Review Issues

Zenodo is an open access platform where anyone can put things¹¹. It is really cool and managed by CERN, but the articles are not peer reviewed. Just like this one isn't.

Journals that have anonymous, qualified scientists look at articles before they are published are peer reviewed journals. This process is essential in establishing trust in the science performed. There are thousands of science journals ranging from genetics¹² to robotics¹³ to stratigraphy¹⁴. Some journals are very impactful and some are not. But they are all peer reviewed.

The fact that this is not peer reviewed immediately disqualifies it from legitimate discussion.

Prior Research on SARS-CoV-2 Evolution

One of the first questions people had when SARS-CoV-2 exploded was, “What is it about this virus at the genetic level that makes it different, and how did it get to that point?”

A number of studies¹⁻⁶ happened very early on so that we could answer this question and move on to the next, more important question of, “How do we beat it?”. They range from looking at the virus's family tree¹⁵ to what explicit mutations happened².

The general consensus of all of these peer reviewed journal articles is that the “[genetic variations in SARS-CoV-2] are likely caused by natural selection besides recombination”¹.

Ethical Concerns Surrounding the Authors

There are four authors. They are all from the “Rule of Law Society and Rule of Law Foundation” and are as follows:

1. Li-Meng Yan (MD, PhD) - lead author
2. Shu Kang (PhD) - no previous publications that I can find

3. Jie Guan (PhD) - no previous publications that I can find
4. Shanchang Hu (PhD) - no previous publications that I can find

The Rule of Law Society is a 501c4 whose mission is “[t]o expose corruption, obstruction, illegality, brutality, false imprisonment, excessive sentencing, harassment, and inhumanity pervasive in the political, legal, business and financial systems of China.”

Figure 1. Screen shot from the front page of the Rule of Law Society taken 2020-09-17 9:13 A.M.. This image depicts Steve Bannon with Chinese billionaire Guo Wengui.

We have known since April that the Trump Administration has been trying to link the SARS-CoV-2 to the Chinese Government to no avail¹⁶. This is concerning in and of itself, but the fact that the authors are funded by an institution backed by Guo Wengui (accused of money laundering, bribery, and rape¹⁷) and managed by Steve Bannon¹⁸ (the same Steve Bannon that was just arrested¹⁹ and charged with fraud²⁰) and his cabal of buddies means that this study should not be mentioned in the same breath as science so as to not besmirch science’s good name.

Holes in the Science

This is the most important section to consider, since even a broken clock is wrong twice per day. It is possible that the authors could be speaking the truth while still having evil sources of funding.

That being said, the main argument is this:

1. The SARS-CoV-2 genome is unique
2. The unique properties of the genome make the virus deadly to us
3. And, **crucially**, the changes in the genome are evidence that these changes were engineered rather than a result of basic evolution.

The authors don't compare the SARS-CoV-2 genome to the RaTG13 genome, but instead they compare it to some others that fit their narrative, specifically ZC45, a genome "discovered by [Chinese] military laboratories".

RaTG13 is a Coronavirus strain, and it is very similar genetically to SARS-CoV-2²¹, but was not studied by Yan. This is the genome that makes the most sense to look at (not ZC45) since it is the most genetically similar one we know of. But fear not! They have a reason for not using RaTG13, stating, "Note that the RaTG13 virus is excluded from this analysis given the strong evidence suggesting that its sequence may have been fabricated and the virus does not exist in nature". This is a *huge* claim that they try to back up with 5 different sources. The only problem is that none of these sources are published in peer-reviewed journals. Therefore this claim is impossible to trust and is worthless. It also completely invalidates the rest of the study since it's proof that they are intentionally cherry-picking their data and not doing their due-diligence.

Next, they claim that the "rare codons associated with this additional sequence suggest the strong possibility that this furin-cleavage site is not the product of natural evolution and could have been inserted into the SARS-CoV-2 genome artificially by techniques other than simple serial passage or multi-strain recombination events inside co-infected tissue cultures or animals."

A codon is three nucleotides in a row. The rare codon they are talking about is CGG. CGG codes for the amino acid arginine. Arginine can be coded by 6 different codons. CGG is the least used in SARS-CoV-2. They say that because this codon is the least used, this is reason to believe that this codon was inserted by humans. This is not great logic. It's like saying, because O-type stars are the least common type of star in the sky, they are probably manufactured.

Next, they talk about the *FauI* restriction site sequence, CCGGC (notice the CGG in the middle there--that's the one they talk about earlier). A restriction site is a place where certain bacterial enzymes are known to cut DNA. These enzymes are very useful because you can chop up DNA at those locations and put your own DNA at those sites. These enzymes are used in labs all over the world. So, since the CGG codon is rare, and it happens to be in a *FauI* restriction site (tautology much?), it must have been put there in a Chinese government lab. This is ... a pretty stupid argument especially since this restriction site is found in three other places throughout the genome (which is the exact *opposite* of what you want when using restriction enzymes: you want that restriction site to be found in only one spot so that you know for certain that you are putting your new genetic material in that one location), and not just this one location in the Spike protein that they are characterizing. Further, this is a method that is not used very often anyway. CRISPR-Cas9 would have been much better.

Lastly, we have a simple thought process on evolution and mutations:

1. SARS-CoV-2 has a genome that is different from other coronavirus genomes.
2. Mutations, if beneficial, can lead to growth of a population.
3. The differences in this genome were clearly beneficial because it led to the growth of the SARS-CoV-2 population.

That's it.

Given how quickly viruses mutate, it makes more sense that the mutations were happenstance rather than man-made. This is further supported by the fact that, if this virus were going to be engineered, using CRISPR-Cas9 would have been far easier, so why use a rarely used restriction enzyme that uses a method that isn't used much anymore? Things don't really add up there.

Perhaps most importantly, there are *huge* differences between the ZC45 and SARS-CoV-2 on a genetic level that *aren't* explained by their lab-made theory. If SARS-CoV-2 *were* based on ZC45, then the genetic similarities between the two should be *huge*, but they aren't.

Conclusion

Their claims followed by my rebuttal supported by the above.

1. If it was a laboratory product, the most critical element in its creation, the backbone/template virus (ZC45/ZXC21), is owned by military research laboratories.
 - a. They deliberately did not include genomes that are more closely related to SARS-CoV-2. This claim is false.

2. The genome sequence of SARS-CoV-2 has likely undergone genetic engineering, through which the virus has gained the ability to target humans with enhanced virulence and infectivity.
 - a. This is a spurious conclusion based on poor analysis.
3. The characteristics and pathogenic effects of SARS-CoV-2 are unprecedented. The virus is highly transmissible, onset-hidden, multi-organ targeting, sequelae-unclear, lethal, and associated with various symptoms and complications.
 - a. The virus evolved in such a way that allowed it to proliferate widely (influenza being the most obvious). This has happened in the past and will happen again.
4. SARS-CoV-2 caused a world-wide pandemic, taking hundreds of thousands of lives and shutting down the global economy. It has a destructive power like no other.
 - a. Yes. But this does not support the claim that it was man-made. It just shows that pandemics can hurt the world. This is not news or specific to China.

References

1. Tang, X. *et al.* On the origin and continuing evolution of SARS-CoV-2. *National Science Review* vol. 7 1012–1023 (2020).
2. Wang, H., Pipes, L. & Nielsen, R. Synonymous mutations and the molecular evolution of SARS-Cov-2 origins. doi:10.1101/2020.04.20.052019.
3. Nakagawa, S. & Miyazawa, T. Genome evolution of SARS-CoV-2 and its virological characteristics. *Inflammation and Regeneration* vol. 40 (2020).
4. Rehman, S. ur, Shafique, L., Ihsan, A. & Liu, Q. Evolutionary Trajectory for the Emergence of Novel Coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. *Pathogens* **9**, 240 (2020).
5. Genetic diversity and evolution of SARS-CoV-2. *Infect. Genet. Evol.* **81**, 104260 (2020).
6. Li, X. *et al.* Evolutionary history, potential intermediate animal host, and cross-species analyses of SARS-CoV-2. *Journal of Medical Virology* vol. 92 602–611 (2020).
7. Forster, P., Forster, L., Renfrew, C. & Forster, M. Reply to Sánchez-Pacheco et al., Chookajorn, and Mavian et al.: Explaining phylogenetic network analysis of SARS-CoV-2

- genomes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* vol. 117 12524–12525 (2020).
8. Johnson, N. Faculty Opinions recommendation of On the origin and continuing evolution of SARS-CoV-2. *Faculty Opinions – Post-Publication Peer Review of the Biomedical Literature* (2020) doi:10.3410/f.737471750.793571979.
 9. Yan, L.-M., Kang, S., Guan, J. & Hu, S. Unusual Features of the SARS-CoV-2 Genome Suggesting Sophisticated Laboratory Modification Rather Than Natural Evolution and Delineation of Its Probable Synthetic Route. (2020) doi:10.5281/zenodo.4028830.
 10. *Satisfying Cake Cutting Video | Hyperrealistic Illusion Cakes*. (2020).
 11. Zenodo - Research. Shared. <https://about.zenodo.org/>.
 12. Nature Genetics. <https://www.nature.com/ng/> (2020).
 13. Robotics. <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/robotics>.
 14. Stratigraphy. <http://www.micropress.org/stratigraphy/>.
 15. Forster, P., Forster, L., Renfrew, C. & Forster, M. Phylogenetic network analysis of SARS-CoV-2 genomes. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **117**, 9241–9243 (2020).
 16. Mazzetti, M., Barnes, J. E., Wong, E. & Goldman, A. Trump Officials Are Said to Press Spies to Link Virus and Wuhan Labs. *The New York Times* (2020).
 17. Hilgers, L. The Mystery of the Exiled Billionaire Whistle-Blower. *The New York Times* (2018).
 18. ‘Artificial coronavirus’ study linked to Steve Bannon and Chinese fugitive Guo Wengui. <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/diplomacy/article/3101832/artificial-coronavirus-study-linked-steve-bannon-and-chinese> (2020).
 19. Helderan, R., Dawsey, J., Shih, G. & Zapotosky, M. How former Trump adviser Steve

Bannon joined forces with a Chinese billionaire who has divided the president's allies. *The Washington Post* (2020).

20. Feuer, A., Rashbaum, W. K. & Haberman, M. Steve Bannon Is Charged With Fraud in We Build the Wall Campaign. *The New York Times* (2020).
21. Zhou, H. *et al.* A Novel Bat Coronavirus Closely Related to SARS-CoV-2 Contains Natural Insertions at the S1/S2 Cleavage Site of the Spike Protein. *Curr. Biol.* **30**, 2196–2203.e3 (2020).